

Research papers

Modeling of an innovative integration of compressed air energy storage (CAES) with high-temperature concentrated solar power (CSP): A comprehensive use-case study[☆]

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A B S T R A C T

The transition to a sustainable energy future requires advanced solutions to address the intermittency of renewable energy sources. This study evaluates a novel integration of a high-temperature air-based Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plant with Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES), aiming to develop a high-efficiency and zero-emission energy storage system that can also provide inertia to the electrical grid. The concept is demonstrated through a comprehensive system-level model developed to simulate the 24-h operation of a reference case, focusing on the design and off-design performance of key components, including the compression/expansion trains, heat exchangers, and packed-bed Thermal Energy Storage (TES). Furthermore, coupling the plant with an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) bottoming cycle and waste heat recovery for industrial applications significantly improves overall efficiency. The concept enables the compression train to operate at lower pressure ratios than adiabatic CAES while operating the expansion train at a high temperature, as the necessary heat is supplied by the solar field, utilizing cost-effective, commercially available equipment. A novel heat exchanger design, inspired by heat recovery steam generators, efficiently integrates atmospheric air from the TES with pressurized air from CAES. Key findings include achieving a Round-Trip Efficiency (RTE) of 43.1 % and an electricity production-to-consumption ratio of 107.8 %, owing to the combined contributions of grid-stored electricity and dispatchable electricity production from solar energy. A comparative analysis of constant pressure versus sliding pressure operation in the expansion train further enhances efficiency. These results position the CAES-CSP concept as a promising solution, and future work will include economic evaluation and optimization to build on these findings.

Nomenclature

CAES	Compressed Air Energy Storage	IPH	Industrial Process Heat
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power	LHEX	Compression Train Intercoolers
LAES	Liquid Air Energy Storage	HHEX	High-Temperature Air-Air Heat Exchanger
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle	DNI	Direct Normal Irradiation
PHES	Pumped Hydro Energy Storage	C	Compression Train
RTE	Round-Trip Efficiency	LMDT	Logarithmic Mean Difference Temperature
eRTE	Electricity Production-to-Consumption Ratio	R_{aux}	Ratio of Auxiliary Consumptions
A-CAES	Adiabatic Compressed Air Energy Storage	m_{re}	Mass inside air reservoir (kg)
TES	Thermal Energy Storage	$\dot{m}_{in}, \dot{m}_{out}$	Mass flow rate inlet/outlet reservoir (kg/s)
HRSG	Heat Recovery Steam Generator	P	Pressure (Pa)
HPT	High-Pressure Turbine	T	Temperature (K)
LPT	Low-Pressure Turbine	V	Volume (m ³)
		Z_{com}	Compressibility factor (–)
		R	Gas constant (J/mol K)

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h	Heat transfer coefficient (W/m^2K)
v_f	Packed-bed uniform velocity (m/s)
U	Global heat transfer coefficient (W/m^2K)
A	Area (m^2)
W	Power (W)
E	Energy (MWh)
\dot{V}	Volumetric flow rate (m^3/s)
ΔP	Pressure drop (Pa)
Nu	Nusselt number ($-$)
Re	Reynolds number ($-$)

Greek letters

ε	Packed-bed porosity ($-$)
ρ	Density (kg/m^3)
c_p	Specific Heat (J/kgK)
κ	Thermal conductivity (W/mK)
η	Efficiency ($-$)

Subscripts

f	Fluid
s	Solid
amb	Ambient
con	Convection fluid-solid
$cross$	Cross area
HEX	Heat exchanger
b	Blower
out, el	Electric output
in, el	Electric input
in, sun	Solar energy input
in, th	Thermal energy input
$out, receiver$	Thermal energy output in receiver
BC	Brayton cycle
aux	Auxiliary consumptions
ch	Charging process
dch	Discharging process
sf	Solar field
REF	Reference - nominal point

Keywords

Concentrated solar power
Compressed air energy storage
Simulation model
CAES
Grid-scale energy storage
Thermodynamic analysis

1. Introduction

Over the past few decades, the need for electricity has dramatically increased and the world's energy system is currently in the transformation process toward a fully renewable and sustainable future. Despite this shift, renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, inherently exhibit intermittency. Therefore, energy storage technology proves to be a viable solution to address this issue, as it efficiently captures surplus energy produced by renewable sources and subsequently releases it to bridge the disparity between energy demand and supply [1].

There is a wide range of energy storage approaches like electrochemical, mechanical, electrical, chemical and thermal [2,3]. Among all, mechanical energy storage systems, including Pumped Hydro Energy Storage (PHES), Liquid Air Energy Storage (LAES) and Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES) are the most suitable for large-scale

applications (from 0.5 to 330 MW_e) [3–6]. The PHES is the most mature technology, although it is highly restricted by orographic conditions. LAES is a technology under development with high potential but has a high complexity and investment cost [7,8]. Research and development of the CAES technology has been considered due to its high reliability, low environmental effect, long lifespan, synchronous inertia and economic feasibility [9,10]. CAES operates by storing electrical energy in the form of compressed air confined in an underground or artificial aboveground reservoir. During periods of high energy demand, stored energy is retrieved by releasing high-pressure air and expanding it through an expansion train to generate electricity.

Given its considerable potential, industry sources estimate that >40 CAES projects are being contemplated worldwide for the following 5–10 years [11]. The existing commercial CAES plants (Huntorf and McIntosh) are based on diabatic CAES where the heat generated during air compression is typically lost to the environment as the compressed air cools down. An external heat source based on fossil fuels is then required for the discharging process. Nevertheless, this concept implies CO₂ emissions during operation, and the Round-Trip Efficiency (RTE) is limited to 40–50 % [5]. To address these drawbacks, Adiabatic Compressed Air Energy Storage (A-CAES) has been proposed, requiring only electrical energy input. In this concept, the heat produced during compression is stored in a Thermal Energy Storage (TES) system and later utilized to heat the air from the reservoir before it undergoes expansion in the turbines [5,12]. Demonstration projects of A-CAES have achieved electricity production-to-consumption ratio (eRTE) of up to 60 %, with theoretical studies suggesting up to 70 %. Although this represents an improvement, it still remains lower than the efficiency of more established battery-based energy storage systems [13]. The highest efficiencies can be attained by increasing the operating temperature of the system [9], but this approach necessitates compression trains capable of operating at higher pressure ratios, significantly increasing system costs [14].

Another approach for eliminating the greenhouse gas emissions and improving the efficiency in the CAES technology is to substitute the combustion chamber with a solar-based heat generation unit [15]. In areas with a high solar resource, Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) aims to play a crucial role and it can be used to integrate additional thermal energy at the inlet of the turbines [16,17]. Furthermore, the integration of CSP provides great synergies since typically, the higher the solar resource, the higher the need for energy storage and grid inertia support due to the high penetration of photovoltaic energy. In addition to supporting energy storage, excess heat from such systems can be repurposed for decarbonizing industrial processes, powering desalination systems, or supporting the renewable production of hydrogen. Therefore, several authors proposed already the integration of solar thermal energy with CAES [15,18–24]. Zhang et al. [22] studied the optimal dispatching strategy of a CSP station coupled with an advanced A-CAES, enhancing the flexibility of the plant and improving the economics of the system operation. Bu et al. [21] evaluated the steady-state thermodynamic performance of an advanced A-CAES-CSP system with an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) as the bottom-cycle, obtaining maximum energy efficiencies of approximately 64.7 %. Alirahmi et al. [19] introduced an innovative configuration integrating the system with hydrogen storage and solar units. In this approach, a portion of the surplus power generated during off-peak periods is used for hydrogen production, serving as fuel in the combustor of a second turbine. The optimization results indicated that the RTE efficiency of the systems is 58.7 %. Kandzi et al. [18] presented a CAES-CSP system based on the combination of a molten salt tower plant and an auto-cascade refrigeration cycle. The techno-economic study indicated an RTE efficiency of 67.5 % and return on investment period shorter than two years. Zaversky et al. [20] presented the configuration proposed in this study, where CAES is integrated with high-temperature (>800 °C) air-based CSP and a packed-bed TES system. This design leverages solar power tower technology, which enables higher solar concentration factors, improved efficiency,

and the greatest potential among CSP technologies for cost reduction [17].

Nevertheless, to the best of the authors' knowledge, the detailed performance of a high-temperature CSP-CAES system has not yet been comprehensively analyzed, particularly with regard to the modeling of off-design operation of critical subcomponents and auxiliary energy consumptions. Thus, this study aims to address a gap in existing literature by conducting an extensive analysis of the thermodynamic performance of the proposed concept and benchmark it against conventional energy storage technologies. The mathematical model blends together algebraic and differential equation sub-models, as well as performance matrix of some key components from previous studies. A case study in Spain is presented, examining the impact of operating conditions and the design/configuration of subcomponents on the overall plant's thermodynamic performance.

2. System description

A graphical schematic of the proposed CAES-CSP of the case study is presented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, representing the charging and discharging process, respectively. During the day, when solar radiation is abundant, the incident solar power is transformed into heat and transferred to the air through an open volumetric air receiver (right-hand side of Fig. 1). In contrast to alternative receiver technologies, this approach offers a cost-effective solution, easy and simple long-term operability, lowest environmental impact and recycling potential [25]. Then, the thermal energy is stored in a high-temperature thermocline TES, which is based on a very low-cost packed bed of rocks. The CAES system is charged when low-price electricity from the grid powers a multi-stage intercooled air compressor train (left-hand side of Fig. 1). The low-temperature heat rejected by the intercoolers can be repurposed to decarbonize industrial processes that commonly require heat at low temperatures (< 200 °C) [26]. Unlike A-CAES, the integration of heat from the solar field in this system presents an opportunity to repurpose the rejected heat for applications beyond storage, such as industrial processes. Once compressed, the air is stored in the compressed air reservoir.

During peak demand periods, when demand for electricity is high, compressed air from the reservoir is released, and the solar heat stored in the TES - through a heat exchanger - is used to increase its temperature, enhancing power output. The High-Temperature Air-Air Heat Exchanger (HHEX) is designed similarly to a conventional Heat Recovery Steam Generator (HRSG), featuring bundles of tubes at varying pressures arranged within a shell through which hot atmospheric air

flows. Future research will investigate the potential to reconfigure this heat exchanger to also serve as the intercoolers for the compression train, thereby optimizing performance and reducing costs. The gas expansion train consists of a regulator valve that adjusts the mass flow rate and pressure to the desired operating conditions, followed by the gas turbines – High-Pressure Turbine (HPT) and Low-Pressure Turbine (LPT). In the present case study, an ORC is selected to utilize the waste heat from the turbines, though alternative heat recovery systems, such as a desalination unit or Industrial Process Heat (IPH) supply at higher temperatures (300–500 °C). Additionally, low-temperature waste heat from the HHEX and the bottoming cycle is recovered to supply process heat. Using air as the energy vector eliminates water consumption in the condensation process, making this approach particularly advantageous in water-scarce regions. Depending on the specific application, power scale, and operational constraints, the proposed concept can be optimized and adapted with minimal modifications to suit varying requirements.

2.1. Case study

Among European countries, Spain has recently witnessed one of the most significant increases in the adoption of renewable energy sources, particularly solar photovoltaic, due to the high solar resource available across much of the territory [27]. Consequently, the incorporation of energy storage systems, such as the proposed CAES-CSP system, is crucial for ensuring grid stability and minimizing curtailment. This study focuses on the region of Almeria, which has a high annual direct normal irradiation, and explores the integration of an artificial above-ground air reservoir to overcome geographical constraints. Table 1 summarizes the key features of the plant, derived from a synthesis of information gathered from previous publications and existing CAES and CSP plants [5,11,18,20,28–30]. A medium-scale plant with an electric output of approximately 20 MWe is considered, defining a nominal discharging mass flow rate of 30 kg/s. In the case study, the waste heat is proposed to support the decarbonization of an industrial process [30] (e.g., in the automobile industry [31] or paper industry [32]), where steam in the temperature range of 120–140 °C can be utilized. An additional backup system will be employed to meet the heat demand when the CSP-CAES system is not in operation. The critical subcomponents and boundary conditions of the concept are described as follows.

2.1.1. Charging/discharging times

Among the critical parameters influencing the design of the plant,

Fig. 1. Graphical schematic of the CAES-CSP hybrid system. Charging process.

Fig. 2. Graphical schematic of the CAES-CSP hybrid system. Discharging process.

Table 1
Major parameters of CAES-CSP system.

Parameter	Value
Ambient temperature	25 °C
Ambient pressure	1.01325 bar
Charging time, t_{ch}	6 h
Discharging time, t_{dch}	3 h
Solar field operation time, t_{sf}	10 h
Discharging mass flow	30 kg/s
Air reservoir	Artificial aboveground vessels
Air reservoir volume	2446 m ³
Air reservoir temperature	25 °C
Maximum air reservoir pressure	150 bar
Reference HPT inlet pressure	40 bar
HPT inlet temperature	550 °C
LPT nominal inlet temperature	750 °C
Number of compressors	4
Compressors inlet temperature	45 °C
Nominal isentropic efficiency compressors	84 %
Mechanical efficiency turbines/compressors	97 %
Generators/Motors electric efficiency	97 %
Efficiency blowers	70 %
Bottoming cycle	ORC - Toluene
Air inlet temperature of IPH heat exchanger	140–160 °C
Air outlet temperature of IPH heat exchanger	70 °C

charging and discharging times play a pivotal role, impacting mass flow rates or component sizes. The Huntorf commercial plant and related studies [33–35], have been designed for 8 h of charging and 2 h of discharging. Nevertheless, in response to the recent electricity price profile, commonly referred to as the “duck curve” [36], latest research has suggested shorter charging times of 6–7 h and discharging times of 3–4 h [18,21,37]. Considering the projected electricity grid in Spain in the coming years [38,39], this study adopts a design with 6 h of charging and 3 h of discharging. Although the operation of the plant is inherently variable, Fig. 3 presents the nominal targeted daily electric power of the plant, as well as the available Direct Normal Irradiation (DNI), which serves as the reference for the study and corresponds to a clear-sky day

Fig. 3. Boundary conditions of the daily operation proposed.

on 21st June.

2.1.2. Expansion train operation

The present study focuses on the discharging operation mode of constant inlet pressure of the HPT controlled by a throttling regulator. This operating mode allows the turbine to operate at constant expansion ratio – thus remaining at the design point with maximum efficiency – for the entire discharge process. The reference inlet pressure has been set to 40 bar, which is the most common value used in the literature, primarily due to the Huntorf plant [4,5,9]. Nevertheless, throttling significantly reduces the potential of stored energy and generates exergy losses. To enhance overall efficiency, in the last section, the reference case is compared against a sliding pressure operation mode, where the HPT inlet pressure adjusts to match the air reservoir pressure, eliminating the need for throttling during most of the process. Nevertheless, because the turbine operates off-design in the sliding-pressure mode, its efficiency is

reduced [40]. At the start of the discharging phase, a throttling valve is still required to cap the inlet pressure at its maximum allowable value due to technological limitations. Among the various off-design adjustment methods available [41], variable turbine geometry has been selected to achieve a smooth efficiency curve and to maintain turbine operation at a constant rotational speed.

This study incorporates a preliminary turbomachinery design based on the expertise of industrial manufacturers, which constitutes a novel contribution compared to the general nondimensional performance curves commonly used in the literature [42,43]. The first advanced configuration involves integrating a control stage with partial admission (adjustable nozzle) to operate the HPT under constant mass flow rate. The second configuration aims to increase the overall efficiency by maintaining a constant volumetric flow rate, which results in a decreasing mass flow rate throughout the discharging process due to the reduction in air density as the reservoir pressure drops.

2.1.3. Thermal energy storage (TES) systems

Basalt rocks are proposed as a low-cost and environmentally friendly storage material, with thermal properties assumed to be constant [44]. The pressure drop across the TES becomes a critical parameter in the design process as it might account for a significant portion of the auxiliary consumptions of the plant. Therefore, the size of the rocks has been optimized to maintain the pressure drop within the atmospheric air loops in the range of 3–5 kPa [29]. The TES tank dimensions are optimized for the study to avoid excessive outlet temperature decrease. Additionally, a fixed ratio between the height and the diameter of 0.5 is considered, balancing efficiency and cost based on typical literature values [45–47]. Table 2 summarize the main parameters considered.

2.1.4. Concentrated solar power (CSP) subsystem

The solar to thermal efficiency is governed by two factors, (i) the optical efficiency of the solar field and (ii) the efficiency of the open volumetric air receiver. The modeling of the CSP subsystem in the present study is based on the results obtained in the Horizon 2020 CAPTURE project where several configurations of solar fields and boundary conditions were analyzed [29,48]. To avoid excessive heat losses, material limitations and elevated costs, the operating temperature of the receiver has been limited to 800 °C and its efficiency is calculated with a solar flux mean concentration ratio of 500 [48]. Regarding the solar field, the bigger the size, the lower the optical efficiency is. The size of the solar field has been calculated to charge the TES in a solar time of 10 h. A north orientation configuration is assumed and solar field is generated through CRS4 algorithm [49]. The performance of the solar field is interpolated from the optimal results of CAPTURE project. The solar energy received depends on the direct normal irradiation, as well as the azimuth and zenith angles at each time step [29]. The key parameters considered in CSP subsystem are listed in Table 3.

2.1.5. Air reservoirs

The concept focuses on a constant volume approach to store pressurized air. Conventional CAES have been typically associated with large-scale underground air reservoirs in solution-mined caverns in salt domes. However, to overcome location constraints, artificial storage vessels have recently been proposed for medium and small-scale power

Table 2
Major parameters of packed-bed thermal energy storage systems.

Parameter	Value
Storage Material	Basalt
Basalt - Density - ρ_s	2900 kg/m ³
Basalt - Specific heat capacity - c_p	1000 J/kg K
Basalt - Thermal conductivity - k_s	1.7 W/m K
Tanks ratio H/D	0.5
Overall heat losses coefficient to ambient - U_{amb}	0.35 W/m ² K
Maximum operating temperature of blowers	200 °C

Table 3
Major parameters of CSP subsystem.

Parameter	Value
Latitude	37.1°
Longitude	−2.4°
Effective solar flux concentration ratio	500
Receiver outlet temperature	800 °C
Receiver pressure drop	2.5 kPa

plants [9,13]. Underground caverns can typically hold pressures in the range of 70–80 bar [5,9]. Nevertheless, in order to reduce the required volume, when applying artificial vessels, it is necessary to increase the maximum pressure up to 100–200 bar, 150 bar has been selected for the present case study [14,50].

However, the structural requirements of conventional high-pressure air tanks lead to large wall thicknesses and elevated costs. The most cost-effective solution for small-scale air storage volumes (<50–100 m³) can be the connection of seamless gas cylinders used in industry with small-diameter high pressure piping. The estimated cost of this solution is very close to the actual material cost of each cylinder and can be seen as the lower bound. Nevertheless, when thinking about larger storage volumes as needed for the here presented power plant size, a suitable solution could be the application of arrays of high-pressure pipes that are connected to form one large volume [50]. It is likely that the specific cost will be very similar to that of industrial gas cylinders in the oil and gas industry [50].

3. Mathematical modeling

In this section, the mathematical models corresponding to each subsystem are presented, underlying the assumptions adopted. The model has been implemented in Modelica language [51] and subsequently simulated applying the differential-algebraic system solver DASSL [52,53]. As detailed below, the performance of certain sub-components has been externally calculated and integrated into Dymola as interpolation matrices. The following main assumptions are considered [14,18,19,45]:

- The potential and kinematic energy values are ignored
- The pressure drop in compressed air is neglected
- Air reservoir temperature remains at ambient temperature during charging and discharging processes
- Atmospheric air is considered to behave as an ideal gas, while dry real gas is assumed for compressed air

The air properties are obtained from LibHuAir [54], with temperature differences of up to 6.7 % observed when comparing against the ideal gas assumption, primarily due to the high-pressure operation of certain subcomponents.

3.1. Gas turbomachinery

Many studies assume constant internal efficiencies of the gas turbomachinery [42,55], but this study considers off-design performance by applying variable isentropic efficiencies. The applied mechanical efficiency of the turbomachinery and the electrical efficiency of the motors/generators are 97 % [48].

3.1.1. Compression train

A typical configuration found in the literature [42,56], consisting of a compression train with four centrifugal compressors (C1, C2, C3, and C4) and intercoolers, is proposed in order to obtain low pressure ratios and outlet temperatures (<150–200 °C) with cost-effective state-of-the-art technology [57,58]. In this paper, general dimensionless curves based on experimental data are employed for assessing the off-design

performance [28,56,59,60], and the characteristic parameters are specified for centrifugal compressors [56]. The nominal total pressure ratio – when the pressure tank reaches 150 bar - is equally divided among the four compressors and the mass flow rate is maximized during the entire charging process in order to take advantage of the lowest electricity prices. Thus, compressors work under nominal rotating speed.

3.1.2. High-pressure turbine (HPT)

A more refined design study has been conducted to evaluate the performance of the HPT since it is considered that general dimensionless curves are deemed insufficiently accurate for assessing the various operation strategies. The HPT is designed as a multi-stage single-casing turbine with gearbox. The inlet mass flow rate is controlled by a partial admission governing stage, inlet pressure is controlled by an upstream reducing station and control and main stop valve. Specialized custom software developed by Doosan Škoda Power, known as PowerCycle, which adheres to industrial standards for turbomachinery design, has been employed.

The PowerCycle software conducts heat balance calculations and 1D analysis of flow path design using a blade row approach [61], with air properties obtained from REFPROP 10 [62]. It employs a 1D mean-line calculation method, further enhanced by three streamline recalculations extending to the root and tip within each stage. The simulation encompasses subcomponents such as the stator blade, rotor blade, rotor sealing, tip sealing, and interstage diffusers. The boundary conditions provided to the tools include the inlet mass flow rate, pressure, temperature, and outlet pressure. Based on these inputs, an iterative methodology is applied to design the flow path. Subsequently, geometric parameters such as blade angles, chord lengths, and expected efficiencies are calculated. The shaft speed is then iteratively refined to optimize the overall performance and achieve maximum efficiency. The software incorporates an internal loss model grounded in physical principles, numerical simulations, and experimental data [63,64]. Sealing leakage estimations are based on the models proposed by Samoylovich [65] and Zalf [66], with adjustments derived from internal experimental testing [67]. The design of the control stage with partial admission is also reconfirmed by internal experimental testing. Isentropic efficiency obtained for the results of the reference case is 90.3 % (see Table 11).

3.1.3. Low-pressure turbine (LPT)

The LPT is designed as a multi-stage single-cylinder turbine and its operation has been set to a constant inlet pressure. This inlet pressure affects the electric output of the HPT, the LPT and the Rankine cycle. Therefore, optimizing this parameter is critical for overall system performance. Various LPT designs have been proposed to accommodate different pressure ratios, varying the inlet pressure between 3 and 10 bar to facilitate the integration of conventional technology. The nominal inlet temperature is set to 750 °C, although the inlet temperature slightly decreases as the outlet temperature of the TES is reduced. The AxSTREAM® [68] software has been employed, a platform for multi-disciplinary design, analysis and optimization that provides an integrated and streamlined approach to turbomachinery design, and extensively validated against reference industrial data. The software allows selecting a set of variables and then builds surrogate models to optimize integral flow path parameters. The tool explores different design plans of experiments, such as Box-Behnken's approximation plan and Rechtschafner's interpolation plan, to analyze the dependencies of input and output parameters.

The geometric parameters—such as the number of stages, diameters, blade height, and first-stage blade angle—as well as aerodynamic criteria, including stage hub reactivity and Parson's number, were defined using the AxSTREAM® Preliminary Design module. From these data, combinations of design parameters were generated using quasi-random search algorithms (LPr-search) [69]. For each combination of

design parameters, a complete turbine flow path design was created. The performance of turbine designs was assessed using meanline analysis for the direct task calculation, with energy losses estimated through the Craig Cox model [70]. The selected flow path variant was then further refined: the blade geometry and the distribution of thermodynamic and kinematic parameters of the working fluid were analyzed using the 1D/2D Streamline Solver. Finally, the design was optimized using multi-criteria, multiparameter optimization algorithms available in the AxPLANTM module, based on Design of Experiments (DoE) methods [71], with the goal of maximizing turbine efficiency.

3.2. Organic Rankine cycle (ORC)

In the present case study, the integration of an ORC is proposed to achieve higher electricity power output. Additionally, to boost efficiency of the cycle, a recuperative ORC cycle is used. Toluene (ODP 0, GWP 3) was selected as the working fluid for this study due to its suitability for the operating temperature range and its alignment with findings in existing literature [72]. This choice complies with current European regulations, excluding ozone-depleting substances (Annex I, Regulation No. 590/2024) [73] and fluorocarbons (Regulation No. 573/2024) [74]. However, it is important to note that the condensation pressure of toluene is below atmospheric pressure, which may lead to air infiltration—a critical consideration when using flammable working fluids like toluene. Future studies will systematically evaluate the selection of working fluids, focusing on optimizing the ORC performance while considering practical and operational constraints, such as safety, environmental impact, and system reliability.

Table 4 summarizes the assumptions made for the thermodynamic evaluation of the ORC based on the existing literature [72,75]. The inlet conditions of the ORC turbine, including both pressure and temperature, have been optimized to maximize electric power output across a range of air inlet temperatures. Furthermore, the air outlet temperature is maintained above 150 °C to ensure adequate heat supply to the IPH. The model has been developed using a specific software called IPSEpro, that enables steady-state heat balances in energy systems [76].

3.3. Pressurized air reservoir

The modeling of the compressed air reservoir relies on mass balance eq. (1) for calculating the transient dynamics of air mass. The pressure within the compressed air reservoir has been obtained with the eq. (2), considering a compressibility factor Z_{com} based on the Berthelot gas state equation and obtaining values of 0.977–0.994 [77].

$$\frac{dm_{re}}{dt} = \dot{m}_{in} - \dot{m}_{out} \quad (1)$$

$$P = \frac{m_{re}RTZ_{com}}{V} \quad (2)$$

Due to the expected high number of aboveground vessels and the high corresponding heat losses, the temperature of the air inside the air reservoir is considered to be equal to the ambient temperature, 25 °C [14,18].

3.4. Packed-bed thermal energy storage (TES)

The presented subcomponent is based on a non-equilibrium model with one-dimensional spatial resolution along the packed-bed length z , achieving a balance between computational efficiency and a minor reduction in accuracy. Additional assumptions are made: (i) conduction within the rocks is neglected, assuming a uniform temperature; (ii) packed-bed with homogeneous distribution and particles, (iii) heat losses in radial direction only and (iv) dry ideal gas is considered for obtaining fluid properties [78].

The modified Schumann [79] equations used in this work consists of

Table 4
Boundary conditions of ORC [72,75].

Parameter	Value
Ambient temperature	25 °C
Air inlet temperature	300–600 °C
Air mass flow	30 kg/s
Pinch Point in HRSG	10 °C
Pinch Point in regenerator	10 °C
Condenser pressure	0.1 bar
Condenser subcooling temperature	3 °C
Condenser fan efficiency	80 %
Isentropic efficiency of ORC turbine	80 %
Isentropic efficiency of feed pumps	70 %
Efficiency of electric motors and generator	97 %
HRSG pressure drop in air side	0.015 bar
HRSG pressure drop in toluene side	0.75 bar
Regenerator pressure drop	0.03 bar
Condenser pressure drop in air side	0.002 bar

two energy equations, one for the fluid (3) and the other for the solid particles (4). Further information of the submodel can be found in Hernández et al. [80].

$$\varepsilon \cdot \rho_f \cdot c_{p_f} \cdot \left(\frac{\delta T_f}{\delta t} + v_f \cdot \frac{\delta T_f}{\delta z} \right) = k_{f_e} \cdot \frac{\delta^2 T_f}{\delta z^2} + h_{con} \cdot (T_s - T_f) - U_{amb} \cdot (T_f - T_{amb}) \quad (3)$$

$$(1 - \varepsilon) \cdot \rho_s \cdot c_{p_s} \cdot \frac{\delta T_s}{\delta t} = k_{s_e} \cdot \frac{\delta^2 T_s}{\delta z^2} + h_{con} \cdot (T_f - T_s) \quad (4)$$

Both equations incorporates the sum of the rate of change of enthalpy, a term associated with axial conductive heat transfer (with the effective thermal conductivities defined as $k_{f_e} = \varepsilon \cdot k_f$ and $k_{s_e} = (1 - \varepsilon) \cdot k_s$ [81]) and another term that accounts for heat exchange by convection between the particles and the fluid. Additionally, (3) includes the sum of the rate of change of enthalpy associated with fluid flow (considering a uniform velocity

$v_f = \frac{\dot{m}_{TES}}{\varepsilon \cdot \rho_f \cdot A_{cross}}$ throughout the packed-bed) and a component that considers thermal losses to the surroundings.

This approach has been employed in prior studies and, in particular, there are several empirical relationships to determine h_{con} , which is one of the most relevant parameters of the model [82,83]. Achenbach correlation [84] has been selected for the present simulations, as it is currently regarded as the most accurate method applicable to packed-bed TES utilizing air under laminar flow conditions [47]:

$$Nu = \left[(1.18Re^{0.58})^4 + \left(0.23 \left(\frac{1}{1 - \varepsilon} \right)^{0.75} \right)^4 \right]^{1/4} \quad (5)$$

Pressure drop across the packed-bed TES is calculated using Ergun's equation [85]. Sensitivity analysis of the model indicates that a discretization of 250 nodes provides a reasonable computational cost while achieving a root mean square error of <3.5 %. The initial temperature values in the TES – from the previous day - have been calculated by considering the cyclic behavior of the plant, reaching a thermal storage efficiency of 97 %.

3.5. Compression train intercoolers

The low-temperature air-air intercoolers are designed as shell and tube heat exchangers, where pressurized air flows inside the tubes. A detailed design has been carried out, using CC-THERM (Version 5.6) from ChemCAD software [86]. In the entire plant model the performance of the heat exchangers has been modelled through the Logarithmic Mean Difference Temperature (LMDT), eq. (6), estimating the overall heat transfer coefficient (U_{HEX}) and the heat transfer area (A_{HEX}).

$$\dot{Q}_{HEX} = U_{HEX} A_{HEX} \Delta T_{LMDT} \quad (6)$$

To avoid excessive auxiliary consumptions, a maximum pressure drops of 4 kPa in the atmospheric air flow is imposed [29]. The design of the tubes is based on available guidelines [87,88] and a shell type of TEMA E is chosen. The off-design performance of the heat exchangers has been modelled in ChemCAD, with the results integrated into Dymola as a variable U_{HEX} .

3.6. High-temperature air-air heat exchanger (HHEX)

Due to the high operating pressures and temperatures, instead of considering conventional shell-and-tubes configuration, the proposed HHEX is designed to resemble a conventional heat recovery steam generator. It features tube bundles operating at different pressures, arranged within a shell through which hot atmospheric air from the TES flows. To improve efficiency, a parallel configuration of selected tube bundles is also considered.

An in-house software tool has been developed to model and design the HHEX, incorporating heat transfer and pressure drop correlations from the literature [89]. Thermal properties are calculated based on average temperatures obtained from REFPROP 10 [62]. Parameters such as tube pitch, fin configuration, and tube arrangement are designed in accordance with established standards (e.g., maximum shell-side velocity of 20 m/s) [89], while material selection and tube dimensions adhere to the ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code [90].

3.7. Throttling valve

The throttling process is assumed to be isenthalpic [40], and the outlet temperature of the valve is calculated using the real gas equation of state. At the beginning of the discharging process, when the air pressure is at its maximum, a temperature difference of up to 7 °C is observed between the inlet and outlet streams.

3.8. Auxiliary consumptions

Finally, to calculate the net electricity produced and consumed from the grid, it is necessary to calculate the auxiliary consumptions of the blowers that move the atmospheric air through the plant, (7).

$$\dot{W}_b = \frac{\dot{V}_b \cdot \Delta P_b}{\eta_b} \quad (7)$$

where η_b is the efficiency of the blowers that has been set to 0.7. An additional 1.5 % of pressure drop is included to assume the effect of the piping [29].

3.9. Performance assessment

The proposed breakthrough concept is a hybrid CSP and CAES plant, thus, the performance indicators must be able to compare the plant against the state-of-the-art of both technologies. For this reason, the following figures of merit have been defined.

The Round-Trip-Efficiency (RTE) (8) is calculated as the ratio of the total useful energy output – the net electricity generated, and the heat supplied to the IPH - to the sum of the primary energy inputs: compression electric consumption, auxiliary consumptions and the solar available energy from the solar field.

$$RTE = \frac{E_{out,el} + E_{out,IPH}}{E_{in,el} + E_{in,sun}} = \frac{\int_0^{\Delta T_{ach}} (W_{BC} + W_{ORC} - W_{aux,dch}) dt + \int_0^{\Delta T_{IPH}} W_{IPH} dt}{\int_0^{\Delta T_{ch}} (W_C + W_{aux,ch}) dt + \int_0^{\Delta T_{sf}} W_{DNI} dt} \quad (8)$$

The power plant efficiency (η_{cycle}) only considers the net electricity generated divided by the compression electric power and the thermal

input provided to the power cycle. This parameter allows a fair comparison against conventional diabatic CAES plants (e.g., Huntorf), but replacing the gas consumption with a renewable thermal source.

$$\eta_{\text{cycle}} = \frac{E_{\text{out,el}}}{E_{\text{in,el}} + E_{\text{in,th}}} = \frac{\int_0^{\Delta T_{\text{dch}}} (W_{\text{BC}} + W_{\text{ORC}} - W_{\text{aux,dch}}) dt}{\int_0^{\Delta T_{\text{ch}}} (W_{\text{C}} + W_{\text{aux,ch}}) dt + \int_0^{\Delta T_{\text{dch}}} W_{\text{HHEX,th}} dt} \quad (9)$$

The electricity production-to-consumption ratio (eRTE) is defined as the ratio of net electricity generated in the discharging process to the power consumed during the charging process. It constitutes a crucial index to compare the concept against other only-electric energy storage systems, such as A-CAES.

$$e\text{RTE} = \frac{E_{\text{out,el}}}{E_{\text{in,el}}} = \frac{\int_0^{\Delta T_{\text{dch}}} (W_{\text{BC}} + W_{\text{ORC}} - W_{\text{aux,dch}}) dt}{\int_0^{\Delta T_{\text{ch}}} (W_{\text{C}} + W_{\text{aux,ch}}) dt} \quad (10)$$

Finally, the efficiency of the solar field is evaluated through eq. (11) and the ratio of the auxiliary consumptions are calculated through eq. (12):

$$\eta_{\text{sf}} = \frac{E_{\text{out,receiver}}}{E_{\text{in,sun}}} = \frac{\int_0^{\Delta T_{\text{sf}}} W_{\text{out,receiver}} dt}{\int_0^{\Delta T_{\text{sf}}} W_{\text{DNI}} dt} \quad (11)$$

$$R_{\text{aux}} = \frac{E_{\text{aux,el}}}{E_{\text{out,gross,el}}} = \frac{\int_0^{\Delta T_{\text{dch}}} (W_{\text{aux,dch}}) dt + \int_0^{\Delta T_{\text{ch}}} (W_{\text{aux,ch}}) dt}{\int_0^{\Delta T_{\text{dch}}} (W_{\text{BC}} + W_{\text{ORC}}) dt} \quad (12)$$

3.10. Validation

The system proposed in this study represents a novel conceptual design that has not yet been implemented in practice. As similar methodologies have been reported in the literature, the validation of the model has been carried out by independently verifying each component. The corresponding results are summarized in Table 5. The low percentage errors observed across all subsystems indicate that the model offers an accurate and reliable representation of the proposed system.

4. Results and discussion

This section presents and analyzes the key findings of the study. Initially, the results of each subcomponent are discussed in detail. Subsequently, the overall performance of the entire plant is evaluated and interpreted, demonstrating the potential of the innovative concept.

4.1. Compression train

Fig. 4 illustrates the performance of the compression train. Specifically, figure a) presents the required electric power and mass flow rate during the 6-h charging process, while figure b) depicts the variation in pressure ratio and isentropic efficiency of each compressor. At the beginning of charging, the mass flow rate is 12.6 % higher than its nominal value. As the pressure ratio increases, the mass flow rate decreases and the isentropic efficiency improves, leading to a maximum electric power consumption of 9.78 MWe at around 14:30. This configuration reveals that the variation in the charging process is predominantly absorbed by the last compressor, although it operates within conventional conditions. At the start of charging, the isentropic efficiencies of compressors C1, C2, C3, and C4 are 1.2 %, 2.5 %, 5.4 %, and 14.3 % lower than their respective design points, indicating effective performance throughout the process. Moreover, the lower efficiency of C4 is offset by the lower pressure ratio, resulting in slightly reduced energy consumption compared to the other compressors throughout the entire charging process.

4.2. Organic Rankine cycle (ORC)

The optimal performance parameters are summarized in Table 6,

which also facilitates the optimization of the inlet pressure for the low-pressure turbine (LPT), as presented in Section 4.4. The obtained efficiencies are in the range of 24.3–30.3 %, depending on the air inlet temperature.

4.3. Compression train intercoolers

Table 7 presents the specifications of the optimal heat exchangers designed in accordance with TEMA Type E shell standards. The designs utilize conventional carbon steel tubes equipped with Trufin® fins, featuring 630 fins per meter and a fin height of 1.6 mm. Despite the constraints imposed by pressure drop limitations and the intrinsic challenges of air-to-air heat exchangers, the proposed designs demonstrate feasibility, albeit requiring a large surface area. Therefore, further research is recommended to investigate the potential for reconfiguring the HHEX to function also as intercoolers. The U_{REF} values reported in Table 7 correspond to those calculated at the beginning of the charging process. Throughout the entire charging process, as a consequence of non-stationary operations, the intercoolers show a maximum U_{HEX} variation relative to the reference value of 6–20 %, with the highest variation occurring in LHGX4.

4.4. Low-pressure turbine

The optimal designs of the LPT under different constant inlet pressures are presented in Table 8. The results indicate that higher inlet pressures correspond to higher isentropic efficiencies and lead to greater axial lengths due to the increased number of stages required. To maximize the usage of the TES, as the outlet temperature decreases, the inlet temperature of the LPT decreases up to 700 °C, where off-design performance maintains consistent efficiency while allowing a smaller TES and solar field size. Nevertheless, in this section, the impact of the inlet pressure of the LPT has been evaluated under nominal discharging operation conditions with inlet temperature equal to 750 °C.

Fig. 5 shows the variation in the outlet temperature of both turbines and the inlet temperature of the ORC, which remain within acceptable and conventional ranges. As shown in Fig. 6, increasing the LPT inlet pressure boosts its electric power output but reduces the HPT's power due to a lower pressure ratio and the ORC electric power due to a lower inlet temperature. Fig. 7 depicts the total gross electric power, revealing slight variation. The optimal LPT inlet pressure is identified as 6 bar, yielding a total gross electric power output of 21.6 MWe at nominal point. This pressure optimizes the balance between turbine performance and overall system efficiency.

4.5. High-temperature air-air heat exchanger (HHEX)

Fig. 8 illustrates the schematic configuration of the proposed HHEX, which consists of three sections: High Pressure (HHEX-HP), Medium Pressure (HHEX-MP), and Low Pressure (HHEX-LP). To enhance overall efficiency, the HHEX-LP section is preceded by an additional bundle of tubes arranged in parallel with the HHEX-MP.

Given the high operating temperatures, the HHEX-LP is constructed using SA-213 TP347H tubes with a bare design, while the HHEX-HP, HHEX-MP and HHEX-LPpre sections are made with SA-213 T91 tubes featuring solid fins. These fins have a density of 100 fins per meter, a height of 8 mm, and a thickness of 2 mm. The shell design is 5 m in width and 5 m in height. The sections are connected at the top surface of the shell, with the tube bundles arranged in parallel rows and serpentine configurations. The tubes are positioned transversely to the flow and configured with a specific number of turns and with an in-line arrangement.

The HHEX design presents a total area of 8720 m² and a total shell length of 7.1 m (see Table 9). The atmospheric pressure drop of 1.44 kPa and the global heat transfer coefficients – primary limited by the heat transfer in the atmospheric side – are aligned with the typical HRSG

Table 5
Validation of modelled subcomponents through comparison with literature.

Component		Present work	Reference	Error (%)	Comment
Open Volumetric Air Receiver	Outlet temperature (°C)	776	766	1.3	Validated experimentally under varying outlet temperatures and solar flux conditions [91]
Solar Field	Solar Efficiency (%)	71.9	71.3	0.9	Based on computational models and a heliostat field generation algorithm [49]
Thermal Energy Storage	Root Mean Square Error of temperature distribution (%)	–	–	6.3	Validated experimentally using a packed-bed thermocline with air; temperature profile measured at different heights within the TES unit [47]
Compression Train	Compression Energy (MWh)	1046	996	5.1	Modelled under off-design conditions using generalized compressor performance formula [28]
Compression Train Intercoolers	Optimum Heat Transfer Surface (W/m ² K)	60.3	60.2	0.2	Optimum design obtained from commercial ChemCad software is compared against literature [92]
High-Temperature Air-Air Heat Exchanger	Global Heat Transfer Coefficient (W/m ² K)	61	61.8	1.3	Heat transfer performance benchmarked against existing HRSG of a combined cycle power plant [93]
High Pressure Turbine	Heat Transfer Surface (W/m ² K)	1843.5	1805.4	2.1	Comparison of in-house software from Doosan Škoda Power and measured turbine output [94]
	Shaft power (MW)	1006	1000	0.6	
High Pressure Turbine	Relative stator blade throats (mid-span) (%)	99.78	100	0.2	Based on geometric comparison of designed vs. manufactured blade throats using 3D optical scanning [95]
Low Pressure Turbine	Shaft power (MW)	18.4	17.9	2.8	Commercial AxSTREAM® software validated against a detailed Computational Fluid Dynamics model [96]
	Root Mean Square Error of off-design efficiency (%)	–	–	2.4	
Organic Rankine Cycle	Efficiency (%)	32.8	32.5	0.7	Validated against modelled toluene-based ORC system integrated with CAES [72]

Fig. 4. Compression train performance. (a) Compression electric power and mass flow rate. (b) Pressure ratio and isentropic efficiency of each compressor.

Table 6
ORC performance as function of air inlet temperature specific net power and net efficiency).

Air Inlet Temperature (°C)	300	350	400	450	500	550	600
Turbine inlet pressure (bar)	8	21	26	24	16	16	16
Turbine inlet temperature (°C)	220	270	310	320	330	360	380
Electric power output (MWe)	0.97	1.57	2.17	2.57	2.84	3.25	3.69
Cycle efficiency (%)	24.3	25.2	27.7	28.3	28.1	29.5	30.3
Air Outlet Temperature (°C)	152.7	151.3	150.5	162.6	183.1	207.4	223.8

Table 7
Compression Train Intercoolers specifications.

Heat Exchanger	Length (m)	Shell diameter (m)	Number of tubes	Outer tubes diameter (m)	Total heat transfer surface - A_{HEX} (m ²)	Global reference heat transfer coefficient - U_{REF} (W/m ² K)
LHEX1	6.1	1.7	3214	0.0158	3111	23.2
LHEX2	8.5	1.4	2102	0.0158	2854	31.2
LHEX3	7.3	1.4	2102	0.0158	2444	30.2
LHEX4	8.5	1.4	2102	0.0158	2854	31.5

Table 8
LPT performance for different inlet pressure.

Parameter	3 bar	4 bar	6 bar	8 bar	10 bar
Efficiency (%)	83.7	85.8	87.2	87.5	87.8
Shaft speed (rpm)	3000	3000	3000	3000	3000
Stages number (-)	3	5	7	8	9
Axial length (mm)	494	769	1010	1127	1223
Last blade tip diameter (mm)	1651	1517	1417	1381	1352

values [89]. At the nominal discharging point the atmospheric flow rate is 48.6 kg/s, the outlet atmospheric temperature 160.2 °C and the pinch point is 62.8 °C. In the off-design operation, as the inlet temperature from the TES is decreased, the inlet temperature of the LPT is decreased to maintain an approximately constant atmospheric mass flow rate and outlet atmospheric temperature.

4.6. Thermal energy storage (TES) system

A critical consideration in the design of packed-bed TES systems is the pressure drop phenomenon, that defines the minimum allowable rock diameter. Fig. 9 shows the pressure drop in the TES as a function of particle diameter and tank diameter, based on the initial discharging boundary conditions, where pressure drop values are maximum. To ensure the 3-h discharging process while preventing excessive pressure drop, this study specifies a tank diameter of 12.5 m and a particle diameter of 5 mm, resulting in an initial pressure drop of 1.1 kPa.

4.7. Plant operation and performance evaluation

Fig. 10 presents the efficiency of the receiver and the solar-to-thermal efficiency including the optical performance of the solar field. It is observed that the operating temperature of 800 °C leads to an almost constant receiver efficiency of 80.8 %. In order to ensure 10 h of solar field operation, a solar field of 23,500 m² is required and a maximum

Fig. 5. Outlet temperatures of turbines under nominal discharging conditions and different inlet pressures of the LPT.

value of 65.6 % is obtained for the solar-to-thermal efficiency.

The plant operation is illustrated in the Fig. 11. While the target is to maintain a constant power output (see Fig. 3), slight variations occur during the charging and discharging phases due to the off-design performance. TES degradation leads to only a 4.0 % variation in the net electric power delivered to the grid, ensuring grid stability and reliable operation. Additionally, the IPH supply remains stable throughout the process, with a final increase primarily due to the rise in atmospheric mass flow through the HHEX. Fig. 12 shows the variation in the inlet temperatures of the LPT and ORC due to TES degradation, with the variation being more pronounced in the final hour of the discharging process.

Fig. 13 illustrates the auxiliary consumption of the two blowers during plant operation. The higher consumption is attributed to the intercoolers and the supply to the IPH. For the TES blower, it is observed that during discharging, the higher mass flow rates result in greater pressure drops and increased auxiliary consumption compared to charging. The R_{aux} obtained is 6.1 %.

Fig. 14 illustrates the energy flow of the plant. Although the solar filed introduces a notable efficiency penalty with a η_{sf} of 60.8 %, solar energy remains a free and renewable resource with significant potential compared to conventional gas. Furthermore, the receiver exceeds the performance of state-of-the-art high-temperature receivers [25]. The high potential of reutilizing the low-temperature waste heat of the plant is observed, exploiting 55.0 MWh in the industrial process heat application proposed. The net electricity produced is 63.6 MWh, resulting in a RTE of 43.1 % and a eRTE of 107.8 %. The ORC accounts for 10.9 % of the net electricity generated. Thus, thanks to the TES and CAES system, the proposed concept enables highly dispatchable electricity storage. Additionally, depending on the boundary conditions, the concept can be adapted to increase either the fraction of industrial process heat supply – at different operating temperatures - or the electricity produced. Table 10 presents the main performance evaluators of the plant.

With the obtained results, the high potential of the concept is

Fig. 6. Output electric power of HPT, LPT and ORC under nominal discharging conditions and different inlet pressures of LPT.

Fig. 7. Total gross electric power under nominal discharging conditions and different inlet pressures of LPT.

demonstrated. The eRTE exceeds the typical efficiency of A-CAES (60–70 % [5]), and coupled with the reduced cost of the compression train, it is expected to offset the cost of the solar field, ensuring greater overall potential. The plant efficiency, at 40.2 %, aligns closely with state-of-the-art D-CAES systems. While the use of a solar receiver results in lower operating temperatures compared to a combustion chamber

powered by fossil fuels, this limitation is effectively mitigated by the additional electric output from the ORC.

4.8. Industrial process heat (IPH)

Waste heat recovery plays a crucial role in improving system performance. The integration of IPH supply contributes to an increase in round-trip efficiency by 86.5 %, and represents a promising pathway toward industrial decarbonization. Based on the defined boundary conditions, the thermal power delivered to the industrial facility is in the range of 5–8 MWth. Although the power output is relatively stable, an additional backup system is required to ensure heat supply during periods when the CSP-CAES system is either not operational or unable to fully meet the industrial demand. The use of artificial aboveground air reservoirs removes geographical constraints, making it feasible to install the power plant in proximity to the industrial site, provided sufficient space is available. However, the transport of atmospheric air entails additional auxiliary power consumption and piping costs.

Given that most industrial heat demands at 150–200 °C utilize pressurized water as the heat transfer fluid, it is proposed to integrate a water–air heat exchanger into the power facility. This solution is cost-effective, with an estimated investment of 120 €/kW [98], and would allow for direct connection to the steam network of the industrial plant. For transportation, a maximum water velocity of 1.5 m/s is assumed [99], leading to the selection of a DN150 pipeline. The associated pressure drop restricts the feasible distance between the power plant and the industrial site to a few to several kilometers. As a reference, district heating systems — albeit operating at lower temperatures — can reach

Fig. 8. High-Temperature Air-Air Heat Exchanger (HHEX) schematic design and operation at nominal point.

Table 9 High-Temperature Air-Air Heat Exchanger (HHEX) specifications and thermal performance.

Heat Exchanger	Number of tubes (parallel rows x parallel serpentine)	Number of turns per serpentine	Tube	Tube Type	Tube pitch (m)	Total heat transfer surface - A_{HEX} (m ²)	Global reference heat transfer coefficient - U_{REF} (W/m ² K)
HHEX-HP	201 (67 × 3)	4	DN40-SCH160	Finned	0.072	1788	50.0
HHEX-MP	180 (30 × 6)	6	DN32-SCH80	Finned	0.078	2133	51.9
HHEX-LPpre	290 (29 × 10)	4	DN50-SCH30	Finned	0.080	3148	33.4
HHEX-LP	240 (48 × 5)	6	DN65-SCH40	Bare	0.100	1651	49.2

Fig. 9. Pressure drop per length at the TES with different designs at the initial discharging boundary conditions.

distances up to 10 km, often by utilizing waste heat sources (e.g., Gratkorn project in Graz) [100,101].

4.9. Constant pressure VS sliding pressure: High-pressure turbine (HPT)

The gas expansion train—excluding the bottoming cycle and auxiliary consumptions—is analyzed under sliding pressure conditions to assess its performance compared to the reference case previously examined. Table 11 presents the isentropic efficiencies and operating pressure range of the three designs of HPT, operating at constant rotational speed of 6000 rpm. It is demonstrated that the design of the HPT for fixed nominal operation leads to the highest isentropic value, 90.3%. Regarding the sliding pressure operation with constant mass flow rate, a control stage with partial admission through air distribution in four nozzle boxes is designed. The lower the pressure of the air reservoir, the higher the flow area of the control stage. At the beginning of discharging, only two nozzle boxes are open, with the inlet pressure limited to 90

bar. As the pressure decreases to 50 bar, the third nozzle box is opened, and finally, at the nominal turbine inlet pressure of 40 bar, the HPT operates in full admission condition. The effect of the nozzle boxes results in a maximum reduction of 9.4% in isentropic efficiency compared to the nominal point. Finally, the case of sliding pressure with constant volumetric flow (design = 0.616 m³/s) leads to a higher operating pressure range with a maximum inlet pressure of 120 bar. Nevertheless, the obtained isentropic efficiencies are lower than in the other cases and a decrease in the mass flow rate is required throughout the discharging phase, which results in a notable reduction in output power. The performance of the LPT aligns with the values detailed in section 4.4, with the optimum inlet pressure selected at 6 bar and variable inlet temperature (see Fig. 12).

Fig. 15 presents the comparison of the performance of each case during the discharging, including the evolution of the pressure in the air reservoir, the inlet pressure and mass flow rate of the HPT and the electric output power of the gas expansion train. The reference case

Fig. 10. Solar Field performance: Receiver efficiency and solar-to-thermal efficiency.

Fig. 11. Plant Operation. Thermal power and electric power of main subcomponents of the plant.

Fig. 12. Plant operation. Temperature variation: TES, LPT, HPT, ORC.

Fig. 13. Plant Operation. Auxiliary consumptions.

maintains nominal conditions until the decrease in the outlet of the TES, resulting in a maximum electric output power of 19.2 MWe. The sliding pressure strategy with a constant mass flow rate produces a constant electric power of 20.7 MWe while the pressure of the air reservoir is above 90 bar, which then slightly reduces to 18.6 MWe. Finally, in the last case, the process starts with an electric power of 21.1 MWe. However, when the vessel pressure decreases below 120 bar, the reduction in mass flow rate causes a continuous decline in electric power, culminating in a 70.6 % decrease in the output power. This significant reduction may hinder grid integration and complicate system operation.

Table 12 summarizes the comparison of the three strategies. The reduction of the mass flow rate during the discharging of the last case leads to a reduction in the required volume and charged energy. In order to compare the strategies, the ratio of energy discharged in the gas expansion train to energy charged in the compressors have been used as

a figure of merit. Operating under sliding pressure with constant mass flow or constant volumetric flow results in a 6.0 % and 6.9 % increase, respectively, compared to constant pressure operation. Nonetheless, it is also noted that since sliding operation deviates from the nominal pressure ratio, under different boundary conditions, the potential benefits of higher isentropic efficiency in constant pressure operation may counterbalance the sliding mode advantages. Moreover, further research is needed to determine whether this modest improvement justifies the associated factors, such as higher costs, part-load operation of the HHEX, and the increased complexity in both the design and operation of the plant. Upcoming work will provide a more detailed analysis of the system management strategy and the turbine control requirements associated with sliding pressure operation.

Fig. 14. Energy flow diagram of the plant (MWh).

Table 10
Key performance indicators of the plant.

Round-Trip-Efficiency (RTE)	43.1 %
Power plant efficiency (η_{cycle})	40.2 %
Electricity production-to-consumption ratio (eRTE)	107.8 %
Solar-To-Thermal Efficiency (η_{st})	60.8 %
Ratio of auxiliary consumptions (R_{aux})	6.1 %

Table 11
High-Pressure turbine (HPT) isentropic efficiencies under different operation scenarios: (i) Reference case with constant inlet pressure and constant mass flow, (ii) sliding pressure with constant mass flow and (iii) sliding pressure with constant volumetric flow.

High-Pressure Turbine Isentropic Efficiency (%)			
HP Turbine Inlet pressure (bar)	Constant pressure (Reference case)	Sliding Pressure – Constant Mass Flow	Sliding Pressure – Constant Volumetric Flow
40	90.3	89.1	84.4
50	–	89.0	84.0
60	–	85.5	83.6
70	–	82.6	82.9
80	–	80.9	82.1
90	–	80.7	81.1
100	–	–	80.3
110	–	–	79.2
120	–	–	78.4

5. Conclusions

This paper presents the thermodynamic evaluation of a novel concept of air-based high-temperature CSP system integrated with CAES. A preliminary design of the main components - compression train, expansion train, heat exchangers, thermal energy storage, bottoming cycle - has been carried out, and a system-level model has been developed for the 24-h simulation of a medium-scale reference case in Spain. With the obtained results, the high potential of the concept is demonstrated. The key findings are listed in the following:

- The CAES-CSP concept enables the compression train to operate at low pressure ratios, with the necessary heat supplied by the solar

field. A compression train with four compressors is proposed, achieving nominal pressure ratios below 3.5 and isentropic efficiencies ranging from 84 % to 72 % during off-design operation. This confirms one of the key advantages of the concept: the use of efficient, cost-effective, commercially available industrial equipment.

- Despite the challenges posed by the inherent complexity of air-to-air heat exchangers at high operating temperature and pressure, the proposed designs demonstrate feasibility. Shell-and-tube compression train intercoolers and a High-Temperature Air-Air Heat Exchanger (HHEX) similar to a conventional HRSG is proposed. Further research is suggested to investigate the potential for reconfiguring the HHEX to function also as intercoolers.
- An optimal inlet pressure of 6 bar was identified for the Low-Pressure Turbine (LPT), achieving a compromise with the performance of the bottoming cycle. The chosen pressure ensures that operating temperatures remain within acceptable limits and a single-cylinder turbine with seven stages is designed, obtaining an isentropic efficiency of 87.2 % under nominal conditions.
- The solar field required for the proposed plant has an aperture area of 23,500 m². With the open volumetric air receiver operating at 800 °C and maintaining an almost constant efficiency of 80.8 %, the ratio of thermal energy captured to the total available solar energy throughout the day is 60.8 %. The thermal energy storage system is designed with a rock diameter of 5 mm, allowing for efficient heat transfer and acceptable pressure drops.
- The power plant is coupled with an ORC using toluene and with an Industrial Process Heat (IPH) integration to recover waste heat. Despite the limited solar-to-thermal efficiency, a Round-Trip-Efficiency (RTE) of 43.1 % is obtained. Additionally, the electricity production-to-consumption ratio (eRTE) is 107.8 %, presenting a high increment in comparison with A-CAES, thanks to the dispatchability of both TES and CAES systems.
- A preliminary design of the High-Pressure Turbine (HPT) has been carried out to compare its performance under constant pressure with sliding pressure operation, considering both constant mass flow rate and constant volumetric flow rate. Operating the HPT under sliding pressure results in a 6.0–6.9 % increase in the eRTE of the gas turbomachinery, compared to constant pressure operation. However, further research is required to assess whether this improvement

Fig. 15. Comparison of discharging operation strategies. Inlet pressure of HPT, mass flow rate and gas expansion train electric power.

Table 12

Summary of the comparison of discharging operation strategies of the gas expansion train.

Discharging Strategy	Constant pressure (Reference case)	Sliding Pressure – Constant Mass Flow	Sliding Pressure –Constant Volumetric Flow
Required air reservoir volume (m ³)	2446		1688
Charging mass flow (kg/s)	15.6–13.9		10.8–9.6
Charged energy through compression train (MWh _e)	55.8		38.5
Discharging mass flow (kg/s)	30		30–10.3
Discharged energy through gas expansion train (MWh _e)	57.4	60.9	42.4
Ratio of discharged energy/charged energy	102.9 %	109.1 %	110.1 %

justifies the higher costs and the increased complexity in both the design and operation of the plant.

Future work will cover an economic evaluation and multi-objective optimization of the concept to further build on the present findings.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Javier Baigorri: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alessandro Federici:** Validation, Methodology. **Tereza Kubikova:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Theunis Du Toit:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Pablo Rodríguez-deArriba:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Coriolano Salvini:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Conceptualization. **David Sánchez:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Fritz Zaversky:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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